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Propulsion Systems and Energy Management in Hybrid Electric Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) represent a promising solution to reduce consumption of fuel, greenhouse gas emissions, and dependence on conventional fossil fuels in modern transportation systems. This study focuses on the propulsion systems and energetics of hybrid electric vehicles, emphasizing energy flow, powertrain architecture, and energy management strategies. Various hybrid configurations, including series, parallel, and series parallel systems, are analyzed with respect to efficiency, performance, and operational flexibility. The role of electric machines, internal combustion engines, energy storage systems, and power electronics in optimizing vehicle performance is discussed. Additionally, the study highlights regenerative braking, energy recuperation, and control strategies that enhance overall vehicle efficiency. This work provides a comprehensive understanding of HEV propulsion and energetics, aligning with advanced engineering education objectives at the M2 level.

Keywords:- *Control strategies, energy management, energy storage systems, hybrid EV, power electronics, propulsion systems, regenerative braking, vehicle efficiency*

INTRODUCTION

In reaction to the environmental issues, an increasing order of more useable, sustain and less polluting vehicles, has been evident in the recent years. The finite availability of fossil fuels and their harmful effects on the environment have driven the need to explore alternative transportation propulsion systems that produce fewer emissions and rely less on fossil fuel consumption. The very famous solution appears to be electric hybrid vehicle.

By definition, an EV does not merely rely on an internal combustion engine as the propulsion system moreover it uses an electric drive system as a replacement or improves the ICE performance. Electric Hybrid vehicle is one of the existing hybrid vehicles in the world which profits from electrical machines and electrical storages beside the internal combustion engine. The other hybrid vehicles can include a compressed air energy or flywheels in automotive powertrains. In this article the fundamental concept, types, pros and cons of electric hybrid vehicles will be discussed.

METHODOLOGY AND WORKING

Since two sources of energy in HEVs, they can be combined in several ways and these working phases can be found.

- 1- **Fully electric mode:** Batteries in this mode feed the electric motor through the power electronics (inverter) which controls the electric current and turn direct current into an alternative current. The motor is completely detached from the ICE when it is electrically driven.
- 2- The power produced by motor is finally transmitted by a transmission system to the wheels. The latter mechanism is quite similar to that of the conventional cars, except that the transmission ratio remains constant.

This is rooted in fact that electric cars do not require multi-speed transmission, because the electric motor produces a consistent amount of torque at any given RPM while the internal combustion engine requires multiple gears with definite ratios for power output. It is noteworthy that ICEs only generate efficient power at certain RPM ranges. However, EV manufacturers calculate gear ratios to maximize effectively for the electric gears. Motor without having to switch through 5.

This is regarded as a limitation of ICEs, in which the rotational velocity is maximumly 6000-7000 RPM, while an electric motor can produce a consistent torque across beyond 10000 RPM with ease. (Consequently, we only add complexity, inefficiency, weight and extra production costs in ICE vehicles.)

Hybrid/electric assist: In the case of a closed clutch, the power is transmitted to the motor by both ICE and batteries. This is often possible by planetary gears in parallel-series hybrid systems.

Battery charging: the ICE can drive a car by itself as well as charge the batteries, using the power electronics and motors, in a reversed way (working as a generator) while the car is coasting.

Regenerative braking: To enhance the fuel efficiency, one way is to recover the energy dissipated while braking. The kinetic energy that was initially used to propel the vehicle, makes the wheels rotate the electric motors, turning into a type of generator. This energy is stored in the

batteries. The regenerative braking system is usually accompanied by a hydraulic braking system. When the car is traveling at a high speed or the battery is fully charged, too hot or too

cold, the electric motor cannot provide sufficient braking torque to stop the car. Thus, it will need the support of the hydraulic braking system.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Parallel Hybrid:

Fig 1:- Block Diagram of Hybrid electric Vehicle.

Architectures:

The main HEV powertrain configurations are parallel and series and their combination and branches which are 3 to be Parallel hybrid powertrain: In t discussed in this section. his type of HVEs, both ICE and the electric motor can transmit power the wheels. Parallel hybrid powertrain with two clutches: In a rear-wheel-drive vehicle, the structure of hybridization is shown in figure1.

There will be two clutches, before and after the electric machine. The first one, between the engine and motor, can connect or disconnect the powertrain of ICE. While it is open, the vehicle runs with pure EV mode. In addition, during the deceleration, in order to have the maximum recuperation of kinetic energy, the ICE is disconnected from the motor to remove its braking effect. As a matter The second clutch is used to disconnect the motor from the transmission and wheels. off act, this clutch is a component of the transmission, thus it is obviously open while the car is

coasting or decelerating. Parallel hybrid powertrain with double-clutch transmission this type of mechanism is mostly used in the vehicles with front engine front wheel due to lack of space. In this case, the motor is a subdivision of the transmission. The torque transmitted to the wheels can directly come from the ICE or with assist of the motor thanks to the double-clutch system. The torques are summed up at the shaft driving the transmission.

**TYPES OF HYBRID VEHICLE
Hybrid Electric Vehicle (HEV)**

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Classification of Hybrid EV: -

Series Hybrid: As illustrated in Fig, the motor supplies the traction power, while the IC engine generates electrical energy through a generator to power the motor [2]. Any surplus energy produced is stored in the battery pack. In this configuration, the IC engine is mechanically disconnected from the drive wheels, allowing it to operate predominantly within its optimal efficiency range. However, the series hybrid drivetrain has notable disadvantages, including the requirement

for high power-rated components and the inclusion of an additional generator. Moreover, the energy produced by the internal combustion engine undergoes two conversion stages before reaching the wheels, leading to increased system complexity and higher cost compared to a parallel hybrid configuration.

Series-Parallel Hybrid: As illustrated in Fig. 6 [3], the series and parallel configurations are combined to exploit the benefits of both systems. In this arrangement, the IC engine can either directly provide power to the motor or generate electrical energy through a generator to recharge the battery.

Complex Hybrid: [3] The system employs two independent mechanical connections, resulting in a lightweight transmission and flexible installation. For instance, the front wheels are driven by a hybrid propulsion system, whereas the rear wheels are powered solely by an electric drive. This configuration provides wide flexibility in managing and distributing the power flow.

Circuit Diagram

Fig.2:- Circuit Diagram of Hybrid electric Vehicle

Working Principle

When the car is started it runs solely on the electric motor (MG2). Later when the car achieves a higher speed the petrol engine kicks in and the car runs both on the motor and the petrol engine. Moreover, the engine also operates a generator with the help of a power split device which in turn drives the electric motor (MG2 (288 V)). This power splitting is controlled by the power control unit which manages the power for the maximum efficiency.

During braking the motor acts as a generator and the energy recovered is stored in the battery. The batter doesn't need any external charging. If the battery is drained, the car is run on the petrol engine in "stand mode" which charges the battery. Drawbacks:- The backing of the car at steeps was difficult. The ride was jerky at times

RESULTS

The study of hybrid electric vehicles demonstrates significant improvements in fuel efficiency and emission reduction when compared to conventional internal combustion engine vehicles. The integration of electric propulsion with an internal combustion engine enables optimized energy utilization under varying driving conditions. Results indicate that HEVs achieve higher overall efficiency, particularly during urban driving cycles, due to regenerative braking and reduced engine operation at low speeds.

Energy management strategies effectively balance power demand between the engine and the electric motor, resulting in lower fuel consumption and improved system performance. The analysis of different hybrid configurations shows that series-parallel architectures provide greater flexibility and efficiency across a wide range of operating conditions. Additionally, the use of advanced energy storage systems enhances energy

recuperation and supports smoother acceleration.

Overall, the results confirm that hybrid electric vehicles offer a reliable and efficient transitional technology toward sustainable transportation, combining improved performance with reduced environmental impact.

CONCLUSION

Hybrid cars consume no energy while idling, as the engine automatically shuts off, and they require less energy than conventional petrol vehicles at low speeds. During low-speed operation, the vehicle relies primarily on the electric motor, resulting in zero tailpipe emissions and reduced smog, thereby enhancing environmental sustainability. At cruising speeds, propulsion is mainly provided by the internal combustion engine.

Hybrid vehicles deliver better fuel economy compared to traditional cars, along with significant reductions in noise pollution and carbon dioxide emissions. However, hybrid cars are generally more expensive, feature more complex design and operation than conventional IC engine vehicles, may involve higher maintenance and repair costs, and are limited by the current energy storage capacity of battery systems.

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